

Growing Together

A Shared Journey from the NICU to Now

Intro

PREMSTEM is a European Union funded research project investigating human mesenchymal stem cells from donated umbilical cord tissue to treat brain injury related to preterm birth.

Together with our scientific work, communicating with the wider world about the topics of preterm birth and brain injury has been one of our focuses.

We are proud to bring you this illustrated story about two families with children born preterm – a collaboration between researchers, patient representatives, communicators, artists, and most importantly, parents.

Our aim has been to create a realistic story to help families and caregivers to understand how preterm birth may impact their lives.

Of course, every family has a different personal experience and story to tell. In ours, we have chosen to tell Adam and Sophia's stories through the eyes of their parents.

We see that life can be complicated at times, both emotionally and logistically. We see that preterm-born children may sometimes need extra support.

We see many challenges, and we also see hope.

We see how important a support network can be – be it through the friendship of another family, the expertise and compassion of a medical professional, or the dedication and care of a teacher.

When a child is born too soon, there will be no one typical outcome or journey for this child and their family. In our story of Adam and Sophia, our aim has been to portray some of the emotions and steps that may happen, guided by insights from parents and medical professionals with lived experience of preterm birth.

However, it must be acknowledged that the diagnosis and treatment of neurological conditions, such as cerebral palsy and ADHD (attention deficit hyperactivity disorder), differs around the world. Among our authors, we had many discussions around these topics.

We would like to thank the talented artists Fiammetta Ghedini and Maddalena Carrai for bringing this story to life through art.

We would like to thank Pierre Gressens, PREMSTEM's coordinator from Inserm, for supporting the creation of this story and for his inputs into its development.

We also thank Cathy Morgan and Ingrid Honan from the Cerebral Palsy Alliance (CPA) and Helmut Hummler for their feedback.

Finally, a special thank you to Fabiana Bacchini and Lívia Nagy Bonnard. Fabiana and Lívia are dedicated parents of children who were born preterm, and we appreciate immensely their dedication to the creation of this story. Their willingness to share their personal insights has been invaluable.

If your family has been affected by the topics of this story, our partners GFCNI and CPA have a wealth of information on their websites to support families of children born preterm or living with cerebral palsy.

We hope you find this story insightful and encouraging. Remember, you are never alone on your journey.

Megan Finch-Edmondson, Bobbi Fleiss, Teresa Primavesi-Poggio and Hannah Tribe on behalf of the PREMSTEM team

PREMSTEM team

- Fabiana Bacchini, PREMSTEM Patient/Consumer Advisor
- Megan Finch-Edmondson, Cerebral Palsy Alliance
- Bobbi Fleiss, RMIT University
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Hey ladies...

Did anyone ask for snacks?

Fabi,
your banana lassi's
better than mine.

That's because Liv finally
gave me her family's recipe.
The secret's just a pinch
of cardamom and a little...

Hey!
Don't give it
all away!

Eighteen years...
and we're all here.

Hey... what do you think those
four are going on about?

Oh please.
You know
exactly what.

THE NICU!

I never imagined how fast time would pass. Look how far we've all come.

It feels like yesterday we were crying together in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit.

How many weeks?

27... she was born two days ago...

My son, Adam, was born at 31 weeks. We've been here for two weeks now.

You know, I was terrified at first...

But I've learned to really observe Adam, to understand his needs.

I'm exhausted. And scared.

That's completely normal... By the way, I'm Liv.

Fabi.

Remember how we used to talk about the future like it was this distant galaxy?

Like we might never reach it.

The uncertainty was overwhelming. I thought everything I'd dreamed for Sophia was gone.

We were terrified. But we had each other. That made all the difference.

The doctor told us that Sophia's brain scan shows some changes that indicate a brain injury.

I don't know what to say to Liv anymore. I want to be strong... but I can't even picture what tomorrow looks like.

Hey, you don't have to picture it alone. When this is over, I'm bringing Sophia to meet Adam. I've got a feeling they'll hit it off.

Hearing him every day is just the best feeling.

Sophia's feeding can be a challenge. She tires quickly, so we have to go slow.

Some days, when Sophia smiles at me, it makes all the hard moments fade away.

Those smiles are our fuel.

Adam still needs so much care, but his determination amazes us every day.

We keep reminding ourselves progress doesn't always look like we expect.

We started physical therapy last week. It's tiring, but we already feel more optimistic.

The therapists have been such a blessing.

It's a new normal... balancing work, care, and hope.

But sharing this journey with all of you makes it easier to carry.

What does that mean for her future?

It means we have a clearer path now, a plan to help her grow and thrive.

I know this is a lot to take in. But you're not alone. From here, we build a care plan, step by step. We'll bring in a team to support Sophia...

The early intervention team will work with you to help her develop movement, thinking and communication skills.

...They'll work with you to help her gain strength, mobility, and maybe independence.

Will she ever walk? Talk? Go to school?

We can't predict everything. What do you think about having weekly swimming and physiotherapy sessions? You never know...Sophia might turn out to be a future Olympic swimmer or ballet dancer!

Now look at her, strong, joyful, completely herself.

It was the same thing for us: a diagnosis doesn't label your child, it helps us to understand what they need.

Remember Adam's first day of school?

Fabi, it was a disaster. I knew Adam had trouble trying new things, but today... it was clear that he was different from the other kids.

He couldn't stand the sounds of children playing and shouting in the playground, he walked through other children's games without realising.

Then strict rules in the classroom, fast-paced learning, new routines... it overwhelmed him completely, like he was lost in a storm and didn't know how to escape.

The teacher says Adam keeps to himself. He doesn't speak to other children and doesn't even seem interested in them or what they are doing. He just always holds Mister Fogg, like a lifeline.

Even at home, focusing was a battle. Every task felt like climbing a mountain for him.

The rules of playing with other kids, waiting your turn, sharing toys, listening, were hard for Adam. It left him confused and frustrated. He just didn't understand it and couldn't cope.

But we worked with the school to provide support. It helped Adam feel understood, not just different.

You've done an amazing job, Liv. Sometimes the hardest part is just knowing what's really going on.

The wheelchair isn't just about mobility, it will help Sophia save her energy. She won't get as tired moving around. It also supports her posture.

This means she can participate in more activities throughout the day, playing, learning, and being with friends. It's a tool for independence, a way for Sophia to explore her world on her own terms.

But I soon realised it means freedom.

Adam, try saying, "Hi, can I play with you?"
Sharing toys and taking turns helps everyone have fun.

Adam slowly found his way, learning how to reach out and connect. With each small step, his confidence and curiosity blossomed.

So... does your mum know about your crush?

Haha! No way!
Only our classmates know!
But next year, university's calling.
Who knows what'll happen?

I do! I'm going into media studies.
I want to be on the radio!

Perfect!
All you need is your voice.
And your love for music!

HAPPY BIRTHDAY SOPHIA!!!

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